

TRICK's legacy: fostering traceability and circularity approaches in the European Textile Ecosystem

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Summary

This policy brief summarizes the findings from the TRICK project's deliverable D7.8: Relation and Exchange with Other Projects, targeting policymakers. It highlights the collaborative efforts carried out by the TRICK consortium to foster alignment across concepts, technical solutions, and policies, contributing to greater coherence within the European research and policy landscape.

The work emphasizes the efforts done to establish synergies between the ECOSYSTEEX initiative and other EU-funded projects, considering the new regulatory framework and industry readiness. It supports the TRICK's legacy, ensuring an impactful collaboration and innovation. Specially to avoid redundancies, serving as foundation for further research and implementation.

Specifically, this report aims to provide a complete picture of the role of TRICK within the Textile European Ecosystem, highlighting key results obtained and their relevance to existing and upcoming policies. Additionally, the report serves as a bridge between the work carried out and the potential contribution to policies, including references to the specific project documentation for further exploration.

1 The TRICK Project: A Unique Contribution

TRICK is a 3.5-year project funded under the Horizon 2020 program (Grant Agreement No. 958352). Its uniqueness lies in the innovative solutions developed and validated through real-world industrial use cases, addressing critical sectoral needs. The project's main achievements include:

- **An event-based open data model:** Designed based on eBIZ standards, this model is currently undergoing a [CEN CWA process](#), led by ENEA, to formalize its innovative contributions.
- **A Blockchain-enabled platform:** Developed for supply chain data collection, ensuring data immutability and trustworthiness.
- **A business services' portfolio:** Comprising six key services, including the Preferential Certificate of Origin (PCO) co-developed with the Italian Customs Agency (ADM), the Product Environmental Footprint (PEF) service, the Circular Assessment service, the Health Protection service, the Social Lifecycle Assessment (SLCA) service, and an Anti-Counterfeiting service.

TRICK is thus positioned as a pioneering solution to support industry's current needs for the transition to the circular economy. It does so by enabling the efficient and accurate management of value chain data and traceability that will be needed to demonstrate the sustainability and circularity practices required by regulations.

2 Collaborations and exchange

A key objective of Task 7.5 was to foster collaboration between the TRICK project and other initiatives, projects, and solutions. This effort aimed to generate synergies, ensure bilateral impacts, and emphasize the uniqueness of TRICK's results. TRICK's contributions to collaboration and exchange include:

- The participation in over 20 events Disseminating TRICK's results to diverse stakeholders.
- The Cross-contribution to more than 8 exploitable results, enhancing the value and applicability of TRICK's innovations.
- The cooperation with over 5 market-ready traceability solutions, strengthening interoperability and integration with existing technologies.

- The engagement with ECOSYSTE to advance shared goals within the European research and policy landscape.

2.1 The work within ECOSYSTE

In particular, TRICK played a key role in the [ECOSYSTE](#) community, led by the European Textile Platform ([ETP](#)), by actively participating in the working group discussions and events. TRICK was deeply involved in the “TG3 — Ecodesign for Safe and Sustainable Materials, products and processed” working group. The group focuses on addressing sector readiness for the goals outlined in the *Eco-design for Sustainable Products Regulation (ESPR)* and the *Safe and Sustainable by Design (SSbD)* framework. It serves as a discussion space for sharing lessons learned, best practices, and guidelines.

One of the main outcomes of the TG3 working group was a set of mappings of ongoing projects and solutions, identifying the major challenges of these initiative. These mappings provide a snapshot of the current Textile Research ecosystem, highlighting gaps and potential synergies critical for shaping future European R&D roadmaps. All mappings are detailed in the [D7.8 report](#).

2.2 TRICK relevant cross contributions

As part of its work within ECOSYSTE, TRICK made significant efforts to align its data model with those of other projects, notably [PESCO-UP](#) and [CISUTAC](#). These collaborations aimed to enhance interoperability and expand the applicability of TRICK’s data model.

- **Collaboration with PESCO-UP:** the effort focused on mapping the data models and data flows of both projects. By integrating insights from PESCO-UP’s knowledge base, TRICK enriched its perspective on waste flows and sorting processes, improving its capacity to address these aspects.
- **Collaboration with CISUTAC:** This partnership involved identifying and mapping CISUTAC’s selected data points relevant for sorting processes by analyzing how TRICK data model could provide valuable information to support these data points, fostering better alignment between the two initiatives.

3 TRICK’s legacy materials to foster transparency and circularity

The work carried out within the task T7.5 serves also as a reference document to support the project’s legacy and facilitate its integration with other solutions. TRICK main outcomes and key exploitable results are addressed in the following matrix, table 1.

Table 1 TRICK main outcomes and available resources

TRICK outcomes	TRICK legacy materials Documents and References	Leading partner
TRICK data model and ontologies	<p>ENEA summarized report the public available resources in the D7.8 valuable for future collaborations:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - eBIZ Document Factory online and public website with all the technical documentation of the CEN CWA eBIZ specification, containing the official version and the actual draft versio - TRICK data modelling technical documentation: the last update of the eBIZ draft version developed for TRICK project - eBIZ information related to traceability: the reference collaborative processes in eBIZ/TC Upstream (Draft) - Traceability and sustainability DRAFT specifications: examples of the updated eBIZ documents developed to support traceability and transparency processes in TRICK project - Updated list of decoding tables - Dictionary of terms of eBIZ - Relevant documents of eBIZ draft version - Traceability report samples - Transparency and Sustainability report samples_1, 2 	ENEA
Guidelines and best practices of the pilots implementation	<p>Reported in the WP5 deliverables:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - D5.3 and D5.5 for traceability-related practices. - D5.6, D5.7 and D5.8 for pilots' in-depth findings. 	PIACENZA, POLIMI, UPC
TRICK's B2B Marketplace	<p>The documentation for connecting other IT infrastructure to TRICK Business Services and for developing and publishing new services, available in D4.1.</p>	BIBA
TRICK's Architecture	<p>The technical features of the public API belong to the confidential technical reports, D5.3 and D5.5. When required, meetings with potential customers to explain the requirements for the integration will be held.</p>	DOMINA, HOLONIX
TRICK's Blockchain solution	<p>It combines two different open-source Blockchain Technologies:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The Ubitech solution adoption for circular economy is reported in the D5.8 - Quadrans Foundation will provide documentation and smart contract 	UBITECH, QUADRANS

examples to support the integration of blockchain solutions.

TRICK Business Services	<p>The development of the services is detailed in WP4, specifically:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - D4.3 PCO and PEF services - D4.4 Circular Assessment service - D4.6 Health protection service - D4.7 Social and ethical assessment service 	<p>ENEA, DITF, CNR, SINTEF</p>
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4 Policy frameworks and Recommendations

4.1 The policy framework

Under the framework of the [European green deal](#) and the [European Strategy for circular textiles](#), Textiles and Textile products are on the spotlight of the new regulatory landscape. TRICK’s outcomes might have the potential to influence their definition and adoption. Specially, TRICK might have a positive impact on those regulations directly affecting the suppliers and requiring a more transparent value chain. Below, some relevant regulations that will impact the textile industry on the coming year have been identified, as well as the potential contribution from the TRICK project outcomes, table 2.

Table 2 TRICK’s potential impact towards the upcoming regulations

Regulation	TRICK potential impact
Ecodesign for Sustainable Products Regulation (ESPR)	TRICK could provide trustful data to the DPP servers, offering a proof of its truthfulness and support the data collection through its standardized open data model.
Extended Producer Responsibility (EPR)	The upstream information flows modelled in the TRICK project could support the EPR schemes for eco modulation, in line with the framework directive on waste needs of traceability and transparency.
Corporate Sustainability Due Diligence Directive (CSDDD)	The TRICK data model and architecture for traceability support the collection of supply chain data which could support due diligence throughout the supply chain, including environmental and social impacts within a company and its value chain.
REACH Regulation Review	TRICK Health protection service and the TRICK open data model supports the collection of data related to chemical composition or substances of concern in textiles, facilitating compliance with the current and upcoming restrictions.

Directive on Green Claims	TRICK supports the provision of verifiable and trustworthy sustainability data for brands. As well as, helping in the declaration of the data ownership.
The Corporate Sustainability Reporting Directive (CSRD)	TRICK data model for transparency and traceability could support the collection of environmental, social, and governance data in a structured way to support audits preparation.

Specifically, the TRICK consortium put great efforts to align the project outcomes to the Ecodesign for Sustainable products regulation (ESPR) and especially to the Digital Product passport (DPP). A set of recommendations gathered from the TRICK consortium related to the requirements for the preparation of the textile products’ delegated acts were summarized in a position paper. The [document](#) was introduced by [SMI](#) to [EURATEX](#) and contributed to their Digital Product Passport vision. The document emphasizes the role of TRICK on the future development of the DPP and provides a set of recommendations to the identified challenges, summarized in table 3:

Table 3 Summary of recommendations for the DPP development

Information requirements for the DPP	TRICK proposes implementing traceability practices to provide essential information, proposing as set of data points necessary to meet the ESPR requirements.
Confidential information management	TRICK promotes the adoption of data-sharing protocols to guarantee confidentiality of the information to maintain competitiveness by protecting the intellectual property of the companies.
User-specific information	TRICK approached flexible data sharing mechanisms to disclose the information according to user needs, ensuring that sensitive data is not exposed while meeting transparency requirements.
Data exchange standards and interoperability	TRICK introduces a flexible and open data model to accommodate both mandatory and optional information to enable seamless data sharing.

4.2 Gaps, challenges, and benefits

Within the different collaborative efforts organized by the project, a set of challenges of the implementation of traceability practices have been identified. Specifically, the challenges identify key needs for ensuring the adoption and scalability of traceability systems:

- Harmonization in establishing common standards and achieving consensus on the definition and scope of traceability.
- Ensuring data accuracy and reliability across the entire value chain, encompassing waste management.
- Addressing the challenge of extending traceability capacities beyond the EU.
- Ensuring affordable solutions, particularly for SMEs.
- Mitigating the risk of technological obsolescence, ensuring data retrieval even in the event of system obsolescence.
- Efficient data management to assure data interoperability and portability within systems

Within the context of ECOSYSTEMEX, TRICK closed collaborated with other EU founded projects as CISUTAC, CIRPASS2 and PESCO-UP in an interactive session. The main goal was to collaboratively identify the **short-term benefits for having the DPP implemented** and the related information available among four relevant use cases. The activity outcomes are summarized in the table below.

Table 4 Short-term benefits for the

Recycling Business	Reuse Business
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Transparency on composition, chemicals, characterization, and textile properties • Value chain traceability • Feedstock availability and quality to facilitate circular loops • Efficient and optimized recycling processes 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Better assessment for efficient sorting • Life cycle extension • Scalability of reuse business cases • Less waste, and new products entailing a reduction of emissions • More traceability and availability of information such as composition, treatments, usage, cost...
Remanufacturing Business	National Authorities
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Scalability of the repairing business cases • Efficient remanufacturing • Improving the remanufacturing knowledge and feedstock • Available information on the product life cycle • Extend durability 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Effective and efficient market surveillance, ensuring compliance with regulations • Setting targets and strategic incentives supported by the industry insights • Equal levelled playing field assuring the control of the value chain • Facilitating eco-modulation

In addition, consultations were conducted on the types of pilot projects necessary to validate the benefits of implementing the Digital Product Passport (DPP) and the availability of required information. The recommended pilots include:

- **Data transfer and interoperability** pilots testing decentralized data exchange among value chain stakeholders, including manufacturers, brands, and consumers.
- **Data semantics and harmonization** pilots validating the standardization of data meaning and structure.
- Pilots designed to **generate the required data** for DPP across supply chains.
- **Multi-scale pilots** at both small- and large-scale production to ensure traceability across supply chains of varying complexity.
- Pilots focused on **enabling recycling, reuse, and remanufacturing** through DPP.
- Developing pilots to optimize sorting processes for improved recycling outcomes.

5 Recommendations

The TRICK project's legacy has the potential to significantly influence the development and implementation of upcoming regulations. The lessons learned from its pilots and the collective knowledge generated by its partners provide a solid foundation for adopting traceability and circularity approaches in the textile supply chain.

5.1 General Recommendations

From interactive activities and cross-sector engagement, the key recommendations emphasize:

- Promoting **cross-project collaboration** to avoid redundancies and enhance knowledge transfer.
- Encouraging **interdisciplinary collaboration** to foster cooperation among experts from diverse fields to tackle current challenges holistically.
- Ensuring **regulatory clarity and alignment** advocating for coherence in upcoming regulations, such as the *Eco-design for Sustainable Products Regulation (ESPR)* and *Extended Producer Responsibility (EPR)*.
- Enhancing **multi-stakeholder engagement** strengthening collaboration between policymakers, R&D, and industry stakeholders through initiatives like ECOSYSTEMEX.
- Supporting additional **pilot projects** to validate the adoption and scalability of traceability solutions.

5.2 Specific Recommendations for the Digital Product Passport (DPP)

Targeting the DPP for textiles and textile products, as outlined in the DPP position paper, the following key recommendations are provided:

- Introduce the **DPP in phases**, allowing extended transition periods providing financial support to help small and medium enterprises (SMEs) comply with new requirements.
- **Data granularity at the lot level** to allow for accurate control and inspection.
- Adoption of technologies that **guarantee data immutability** for shared information.
- Encourage the creation of systems that support **interoperability**, and seamless data sharing across multiple platforms.
- Establish clear **protocols for managing sensitive information** securely across platforms, guaranteeing data confidentiality.

This report aims to document TRICK's legacy and provide references to facilitate integration efforts.